

The Predictable Rise of “Charged Dark Matter”

How Covert Matter/Hot Grains - Plasma in Dark Mode - is pushing the failures of CDM and MOND into the Plasma-Electromagnetic Cosmological Paradigm

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1st edition: October, 2018

Newest Revision: November 24, 2018

ABSTRACT

The transmogrification of Cold Dark Matter and the Dark Universe in general, into a Plasma-electromagnetic “covert matter” Universe was predicted by the author in 2017 and has begun in earnest. The author details the history of this (in brief), as well as makes predictions about the co-opting of PEMC into Big Bang Cosmology (BBC), and attempts to prepare the PC/EU researcher for the shift and likely battles that will ensue for primacy. A short toolbox of preparedness is presented as well with concrete steps to enhance researcher effectiveness in safeguarding the credit of their work. The incentive caused by mega funding in BBC is briefly analyzed and relayed to demonstrate the *propensity (shi)* of this predicted vector.

Keywords: Dark Matter - Dark Energy - redshift - Electric Universe - Plasma Cosmology - Copyright

Too Predictable

In the age of post-fact, post-modern anti-reductionism, it is all too easy for people to attempt to coerce facts to fit a narrative, rather than the chronology of history and recorded datum. But, it is also easy to predict this behavior, by looking at the outflow of energy in variegated positions (“Shi”) which are being squeezed. In the following paper, a number of demonstrable historical datum are presented, including (1) chronology, (2) grant/funding or research details, and (3) specific papers which demonstrate the shift. The author’s previous (4) predictions are relayed, re-iterated, and (5) a warning is presented to alternative researchers to heed with respect to protecting their research, names, reputations and (6) a toolkit will be presented as to a series of methods to return the volley of attack upon alternative research back upon the mainstream.

The particular issue here is with respect to the *transformation* of the story of Dark Matter slowly into normal, interactive, electrified matter¹, particularly of three kinds listed below and the *prophesied* movement to reallocate credit from original authors and researchers to heretofore DM/DE² (hereafter simply DU for Dark Universe) and potentially MOND researchers (although this process has not begun from their side, yet).

1. Charged “hot grains”/”nano dust”³ ; ie: plasma in dark mode and filamentary structures; aka Covert Matter or Local Matter^{4 5}
2. Baryons^{6 7}
3. Extrasolar Bodies
 - a. Dark/faint Stars⁸
 - b. Y Dwarfs⁹
 - c. Black Body Exoplanetoids¹⁰
 - d. Hot Jupiters¹¹, et al...
 - e. Pseudo-dwarfan stars

The transformation or ex-post-facto alteration of the DU/non-interactive Universe narrative is already well underway and documented with author’s remarks. What is not, and what the author asserts is the *bingfa* related mou (stratagem)¹² to essentially steal the credit for the predictions and claim authorship and primacy, mostly in order to justify continued grant approval.

Some welcome the alteration, hailing it as a change in language that will enable previous researchers recognition and entrance into the vaunted circles of mainstream (ie: peer-review) approval.

The author is a bit cynical in this regard because of the money involved, and historical re-write that has already occurred. But the author is most concerned that certain key researchers will be left out either posthumously or even as they near the tail end of their research careers. The author desires that a similar nod be given as was to J Harlen Bretz be doled out to specific researchers who have come before, in whatever the role. The author fears and feels it likely, based upon the movement of the *Shi*, that such recognition will be hard

¹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.01428.pdf>

² In other words: Big Bang Cosmology mainstream, including new, electrified Black Holes (replacing standard, classical and Hawking Black Holes)

³ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.12502.pdf>

⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1811.07911.pdf>

⁵ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1811.08799.pdf>

⁶ <https://www.newscientist.com/article/2149742-half-the-universes-missing-matter-has-just-been-finally-found/>

⁷ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.12454.pdf>

⁸ <https://www.theguardian.com/science/2016/oct/13/hubble-telescope-universe-galaxies-astronomy>

⁹ <https://www.cfa.harvard.edu/news/su201725>

¹⁰ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.05334.pdf>

¹¹ Many times too close to the star <https://arxiv.org/abs/1801.06117>

¹² Or very convenient subconscious agenda.

forthcoming and difficult to acquire, as young/energetic researchers, who may or may not be ignorant of the previous research reformulate the theories to fit desired narratives that salvage Dark Matter and Big Bang Cosmology (BBC), particularly through the use of inappropriate terms (such as calling Birkeland Currents “magnetic flux ropes”).¹³

¹³ [6]

(1)

Table 1 :: Proper Physics Chronology

Electricity	Ben Franklin	1751
Gaussian Theory	Carl Gauss	1813
Electromagnetism Unification	Michael Faraday	1831
Maxwell's Equations	James Maxwell	1861-62
Quantized Hypothesis	Ludwig Boltzmann	1877
Photoelectric effect	Heinrich Hertz	1887
Electron Theory	JJ Thomson	1897
Quantum Theory	Max Planck	1900
Relativity theory	Henri Poincare	1900-1904
Mass-energy relation	Henri Poincare	1900
Gravity Waves	Henri Poincare	1905
Special Relativity	Albert Einstein	1905
Photoelectric Effect Explained	Albert Einstein	1905
Birkeland Currents	Kristian Birkeland	1908
Atomic Theory Proved	Ernest Rutherford	1911
Particle-Wave Theory of Atoms and Particles	Niels Bohr	1913
General Relativity	Albert Einstein	1915
Proton discovered	Ernest Rutherford	1919
Quantum Radiation Interaction	Paul Dirac	1920
Quantum Mechanics Codified	Born, Heisenberg, Pauli	1924
Plasma Cosmology	Irving Langmuir	1927
Big Bang Cosmology	Georges Lemaitre	1927
Missing Matter ¹⁴	Edward Zwicky	1933
Magnetohydrodynamics	Hannes Alfvén	1940
QEM/QED	Bethe to Feynman	1947-1960
Electroweak Theory	JC Ward	1959
Quarks	M Gell-Mann & G Zweig	1964
Black Hole Theory	John Wheeler	1967
Dark Matter	Rubin & Ford	1970
Electric Star Theory	Ralph Juergens ¹⁵	1972
QCD	Gross, Wilczek, & Politzer	1973
SUSY	Werner Nahm	1978
MOND	Mordehai Milgrom	1982-83
String Theory	Green & Schwarz	1984
Dark Energy	Friedman ¹⁶ or Sivaram ¹⁷	1924 or 1986
M Theory	Edward Witten	1995
Intrinsic Redshift	Halton Arp ¹⁸	1998
MACHOs	unclear	2002? ¹⁹
WIMPs	unclear	2008? ²⁰

¹⁴ Not Dark Matter.

¹⁵ https://www.velikovsky.info/Ralph_Juergens

¹⁶ <http://home.fnal.gov/~skent/early.html>

¹⁷ <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/0809/0809.3364.pdf>

¹⁸ https://www.haltonarp.com/articles/intrinsic_redshifts_in_quasars_and_galaxies.pdf

¹⁹ <http://www.astro.caltech.edu/~george/ay20/ea-wimps-machos.pdf>

²⁰ <https://www.astro.umd.edu/~ssm/darkmatter/WIMPexperiments.html>

Table 2 :: Falsifications

SUSY	2012 ²¹ - 2017 ²²
CDM	2012 ²³ , 2015 ²⁴ , 2016 ²⁵ - 2018 ^{26 27 28 29}
ΛCDM	2010 ³⁰ , 2014 ³¹
WIMPs & MACHOs	2017 ³²
MOND	2018 ^{33 34 35}
Galaxy Rotation and DM	2017 ^{36 37}
Standard Redshift	2017 ^{38 39 40}
Galaxy Rotation and MOND	2018 ⁴¹
Higgs-boson as non-standard Quark	2018 ⁴²
Dark Energy	2018 ⁴³
LDM	2018 ⁴⁴
Standard Accretion	

Note - this table will likely increase in size and scope due to accelerating results from Gaia DR2 and MMS.

(2)

The true scope of money spent on research into BBC is probably not knowable. In this it shares much in common with the worldwide nuclear weapons' programs. Although many facilities are able to be accounted for, the individual grants making up small and medium sized laboratories cannot be all accounted for. Estimates may be taken in the (net) +/- \$1 billion range. Additionally, the funding of journals, generally speaking, is not knowable. Although most journals probably run based upon subscription fees, it would be incredibly naive to imagine that none of them receive grant or gifted money from research interests, vested

²¹ <http://backreaction.blogspot.com/2016/08/the-lhc-nightmare-scenario-has-come-true.html>
²² <https://www.space.com/39001-dark-matter-doesnt-exist-study-suggests.html>
²³ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1204.2546>
²⁴ http://adsabs.harvard.edu/cgi-bin/bib_query?arXiv:1406.4860
²⁵ <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2016arXiv161003854K>
²⁶ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.09823.pdf>
²⁷ <https://academic.oup.com/mnras/article/476/3/3124/4875952>
²⁸ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1807.07113.pdf>
²⁹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.04817.pdf>
³⁰ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1011.0004>
³¹ https://astro.uni-bonn.de/~pavel/kroupa_SciLogs.html
³² <https://phys.org/news/2017-12-machos-dead-wimps-no-showsay-simps.html>
³³ <https://www.physicsforums.com/threads/falsifications-and-constraints-due-to-gw-measurements.929254/>
³⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.04167.pdf>
³⁵ <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1809/1809.09019.pdf>
³⁶ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.10706.pdf>
³⁷ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1811.08843.pdf>
³⁸ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.03298.pdf>
³⁹ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1807.09409>
⁴⁰ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.03888.pdf>
⁴¹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1801.09304.pdf>
⁴² <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-06130-9>
⁴³ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.05027.pdf>
⁴⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.10543.pdf>

interests, NGO or governmental partisan parties (this is particularly an issue in Climate Change research^{45 46 47 48}), etc...

The goal is to demonstrate the preponderance of evidence as to an expectation of behavior regarding the a) saving of careers and b) the continuation of seeking grant funding, even after falsification. It is not provable if such interests interfere in the courts of public opinion⁴⁹ or pseudo-encyclopedic resource sites which report on physics and chemistry news (such as Wikipedia and RationalWiki, in particular). But it is reasonable to anticipate that a mixture of hit pieces (particularly against MOND) along with a steady drumbeat of baseless or even factless articles that misconstrue the current status of BBC would appear, have appeared, and will continue to appear, as if by magical solicitation *on behalf of* aforementioned vested interest groups (VIG for short). A VIG here being defined as those who would otherwise benefit to continue to receive funding and/or support despite falsification.

For example in a previously cited paper, the author had to refute a baseless conjecture that defies all scientific principle. It was stated that a galaxy found without *any* Dark Matter was proof of the existence of DM. This is contrary to a well known principle that absence of evidence is not evidence of either absence or existence, it is simply lack of evidence.

Funding vs. Type of Research or Institution

Figure 1 :: Funding for BBC related projects⁵⁰

⁴⁵ <https://theconversation.com/we-looked-at-1-154-climate-science-results-and-found-no-evidence-of-publication-bias-84500>

⁴⁶ <https://www.epa.gov/research-grants/climate-change-research-grants>

⁴⁷ <https://www.biology.lu.se/research/research-groups/aquatic-ecology/research-projects/publication-bias-in-climate-change-science>

⁴⁸ <https://capitalresearch.org/article/your-tax-dollars-fund-the-global-warming-narrative/>

⁴⁹

<https://www.forbes.com/sites/startswithabang/2017/10/26/even-while-the-world-suffers-investing-in-science-is-non-negotiable/#b42c2fc16470>

⁵⁰ <http://bit.ly/2C0DYrp>

Please note that the CERN statistic is per annum. So the net of \$22.6 billion is not including this budget. Nor is it readily obvious how the entire space program budgets⁵¹ may break down to specifically cover these topics alone⁵². This lack of public transparency isn't really that surprising, given that the funding numbers are astronomical for CERN/LHC while being mostly unproductive. Gaia DR2 has been incredibly productive, helping to study the motions of stars and luminous objects. However, its value has mostly been in showing the problems of previous redshift assumptions.

(3)

The shift to electrical BBC in general began in 2015 and 2016, with the release of calculated values for currents emerging from AGN⁵³, and the discovery of gaseous (charged) "jets" emerging from SGR A* itself⁵⁴.

The existence of currents in space had already been well established in the Io-Jupiter connection⁵⁵, by NASA. However connections were also found between Saturn and its moons⁵⁶, and between the sun and the Earth (called magnetic tunnels or portals)⁵⁷.

Typically the mechanism proposed was related to the movement of a magnetic body through the solar wind⁵⁸, or around another magnetized body⁵⁹.

Separately the discovery and study of "current sheets" in space⁶⁰, operating seemingly without this mechanism⁶¹, startled and intrigued NASA scientists⁶². However, the discussion of Birkeland Currents remains outside the pale⁶³. Often these are misconstrued under the misnomer of "magnetic reconnection."⁶⁴

However, discoveries concerning long galactic size filamentary structures⁶⁵ pushed the concepts of gravity well beyond reasonable limits⁶⁶. Dark Matter was assumed to be the culprit⁶⁷, without evidence⁶⁸. Sometimes, also, mass ejecta such as CME would move at accelerated speeds that seemed to also defy normal fusion based eruptions⁶⁹. Simultaneously previously established limits for minimum star sizes⁷⁰, temperatures⁷¹, gravity/mass⁷², nearby forming exoplanets⁷³, and especially neutron star rotations⁷⁴ were all

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<http://curious.astro.cornell.edu/about-us/150-people-in-astronomy/space-exploration-and-astronauts/general-questions/92-1-how-much-money-is-spent-on-space-exploration-intermediate>

52 https://www.nasa.gov/sites/default/files/atoms/files/fy_2017_nasa_agency_fact_sheet.pdf

53 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1712.08414.pdf>

54 <https://public.nrao.edu/news/origin-of-enigmatic-galactic-center-filaments-revealed/>

55 <https://www.spo.gsfc.nasa.gov/Education/wio.html>

56 https://www.nasa.gov/mission_pages/cassini/multimedia/pia13765.html

57 https://science.nasa.gov/science-news/science-at-nasa/2008/30oct_ftes

58 <https://svs.gsfc.nasa.gov/4680>

59 <https://janus.astro.umd.edu/front/pages/links/lo2.html>

60 <https://phys.org/news/2012-08-thin-current-sheets-space-action.html>

61

http://articles.adsabs.harvard.edu/cgi-bin/nph-iarticle_query?1988ApJ...326..418S&data_type=PDF_HIGH&whole_paper=YES&type=PRINTER&filetype=.pdf

62 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1711.11284.pdf>

63 <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1086/303824/pdf>

64 <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/full/1978Ap%26SS..56....3S>

65 <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2012/05/120517143639.htm>

66 <https://phys.org/news/2017-12-cosmic-filament-probes-galaxy-giant.html>

67 <https://www.iflscience.com/space/astronomers-directly-image-filament-%E2%80%9Ccosmic-web%E2%80%9D-first-time/>

68 <https://www.space.com/16412-dark-matter-filament-galaxy-clusters.html>

69 <https://www.newscientist.com/article/dn7427-solar-radiation-burst-hit-earth-in-record-time/>

70 Previously 12 Jupiters: <https://www.cbc.ca/news/technology/7-earth-like-planets-discovered-1.3992156>

71 <https://www.space.com/12714-coldest-failed-stars-brown-dwarfs-wise.html>

72 <http://www.eniscuola.net/en/2017/07/18/star-smaller-jupiter-discovered/>

73 <https://www.cbc.ca/player/play/882874947810/>

74 <https://www.newscientist.com/article/dn8576-fast-spinning-neutron-star-smashes-speed-limit/>

broken, and with almost no cross examination of the fundamental flaws in the BBC assumptions. Frequently papers continued to write under the assumptions⁷⁵ such as:

1. The Universe is expanding
2. Expansion is accelerating
3. Dark Matter is a real fact, rather than a hypothesis to account for Zwicky's 1933 observation
4. It does not interact, and is non-baryonic
5. Doppler Redshift is purely a matter of distance⁷⁶

In other words, the drumbeat demanding funding for the presumed eventual finding and discovery continued, perhaps fueled by the miraculously, suspiciously convenient confirmation of Gravity Waves⁷⁷ and neutron star collisions⁷⁸ followed by a creation of a black hole⁷⁹, all of which has been extrapolated from what amounts to radio data⁸⁰, and although "independently verified,"⁸¹ the actual imagery⁸² is rather interpretable. It could *also* be a matter of Marklund convection and the formation of a Z-pinch pulsar (basically, a transistor).

This backdrop, however, could not stop the steady stream of disappointing "severe" constraints that arrived one after another in 2016 and 2017 (see Table 2), continuing into 2018 (becoming rather a "crisis" in the words of one writer.⁸³)

After SUSY failed officially and was declared falsified, scientists pitted much of their hopes upon the DU of BBC, or upon MOND. MOND itself began to fail, spectacularly in 2018⁸⁴ ⁸⁵ when it finally officially failed and appears to be beyond the brink of repair⁸⁶. For cosmologies like MOND or SUSY, there appears to be no interest in revival by mainstream BBC enthusiasts⁸⁷. So why does DM and DE continue to receive endless funding (even accelerated, based upon the LZ data) from the US DOE⁸⁸? Indeed, why does it get a pass from media, academia, HEP researchers alike?

Perhaps sometimes scientists, being human, *want* the hypothesis to be real. Much like Aether research which never quite died but merely shifted into an unnatural obsession and delirious love⁸⁹ of the much beguiled and misconstrued concept of "space-time" (as an explanation of the 4D problem Poincare discovered⁹⁰), perhaps this form of understanding BBC, or even the very concept itself is flawed. Certainly, estimations of

⁷⁵ <https://www.uni-bonn.de/news/272-2018>

⁷⁶ <http://www.everythingselectric.com/red-face-shift/>

⁷⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/First_observation_of_gravitational_waves

⁷⁸ <https://www.space.com/38471-gravitational-waves-neutron-star-crashes-discovery-explained.html>

⁷⁹ <https://www.ligo.caltech.edu/news/ligo20170927> it's the author's position that the established "non-physical radius" black hole is not an object but a mathematical region where massive Z-pinching is occurring and charge (the real aether) is accumulated and redistributed.

⁸⁰

https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/thumb/d/db/LIGO_measurement_of_gravitational_waves.svg/499px-LIGO_measurement_of_gravitational_waves.svg.png

⁸¹ <https://www.aps.org/publications/apsnews/updates/ligo-virgo.cfm>

⁸² Note that all images are "simulations" https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/First_observation_of_gravitational_waves

⁸³ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1204.2546>

⁸⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.04167.pdf>

⁸⁵ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1809.09019.pdf>

⁸⁶ Despite attempts, in the opinion of the author <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.10545.pdf>

⁸⁷ Their movements appear limp, deflated, and broken though a few stalwarts will remain.

⁸⁸ https://www.nsf.gov/attachments/242692/public/TurnerKathy_DOEHEPUpdate2_1100AM.pdf

⁸⁹ Much like the Buddha, large numbers of quotes of spiritual or cultural wisdom are often attributed to Einstein, contributing to dangerous messianic treatment of a scientist whose work was, for many decades considered ridiculous and possibly insane by very practical minds (such as Tesla, or Bohr).

⁹⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Henri_Poincar%C3%A9#Three-body_problem

expansion have been riddled with questions. Is it fast enough⁹¹? Is it too fast⁹²? If it's expanding, why is Gaia revealing numbers to be so far off⁹³? And what is with some "jets" appearing to move faster than light⁹⁴?

Others have taken a more critical, mathematical look at the fundamental assumptions of things like General Relativity⁹⁵, black holes⁹⁶, and expansion/CBR⁹⁷. Especially after it came into public awareness that the classic black hole has become so lost and destroyed as a hypothesis⁹⁸, that now completely spurious claims⁹⁹ and ideas take hold in a bewildered, "wild west"-like sea of speculation¹⁰⁰, which ends up, embarrassingly, in mass printed and social media. It also seems to morph as it goes, which is even more embarrassing¹⁰¹.

Although it still attracts some bright young minds, many of those minds will inevitably turn towards *brighter* avenues¹⁰². For the moment, they are undecided¹⁰³. So the mouse spins its wheels and looks for the invisible cheese on the moon. Meanwhile a growing voice calling for a return to lab and in situ results, things which can be measured to be the basis of scientific theory, grows. This is a healthy sign. Mankind has not conquered the Earth, and has little need for inventing extra dimensions and parallel universes which may or may not exist¹⁰⁴, but are definitely beyond our reach. We don't even understand quantum mechanics¹⁰⁵!

(4)

The expected result is simply this: these scientists are not complete fools, and they will be searching, digging, and looking high and low for this "hidden force"¹⁰⁶ that is *actually* responsible for moving baryonic plasma and charged particles around the Universe. And they will find it - have found it¹⁰⁷ - in their "charged hot grains,¹⁰⁸" covert matter¹⁰⁹, and of course, the much misguided in naming: "Charged Dark Matter."¹¹⁰ ¹¹¹ ¹¹²

(5)

So the author must re-iterate: those who have done the work of calculating Birkeland Currents, current sheets, even magnetic flux ropes, need take caution that their own research not be co-opted by a *desperate* population of coerced scientists, eagerly searching outwards.

⁹¹ <https://astronomynow.com/2018/02/23/hubble-data-indicate-universe-growing-faster-than-expected/>

⁹²

<http://www.digitaljournal.com/science/the-expansion-of-the-universe-may-be-much-slower-than-we-thought/article/430558>

⁹³ Ibid.

⁹⁴ <https://www.space.com/41724-neutron-star-merger-superfast-jet.html>

⁹⁵ <https://youtu.be/CnvOybT2WwU>

⁹⁶ <http://vixra.org/pdf/1512.0089v1.pdf> etc...

⁹⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=i8jbu3bSgI>

⁹⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wRsGPq77X0Q>

⁹⁹ <https://news.nationalgeographic.com/2018/04/black-hole-stellar-binary-stars-milky-way-galaxy/>

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.newsweek.com/gravitational-waves-could-collide-sucking-earth-black-hole-1097203>

¹⁰¹ <http://www.pbs.org/wgbh/nova/next/physics/dynamical-dark-matter/>

¹⁰² <https://phys.org/news/2018-03-frustrating-fascinating-world-dark.html>

¹⁰³ <http://blogs.discovermagazine.com/crux/2018/09/21/the-dark-matter-crisis/#.W7IBVLxKjrc>

¹⁰⁴ <https://medium.com/starts-with-a-bang/yes-the-multiverse-is-real-but-it-wont-fix-physics-82beaed322b>

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dEaecUuEqfc>

¹⁰⁶ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.03316.pdf>

¹⁰⁷ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.04376.pdf>

¹⁰⁸ Ibid.

¹⁰⁹ Not to be confused necessarily with Condensed Matter (such as Liquid Metallic Hydrogen)

¹¹⁰ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1804.01092>

¹¹¹ <https://www.cfa.harvard.edu/news/2018-08>

¹¹² <https://www.space.com/40768-does-dark-matter-have-electric-charge.html>

Looking again at Table 1, one must notice that in 1927 it was not only Big Bang which was born, but also Plasma Cosmology. And while BBC was approved by the proto-messiah Einstein at a single lecture given by Lemaitre, PC (PEMC) was proved in terrella experiments that go back to Gilbert (1600)¹¹³, Birkeland, Langmuir, and of course re-proposed by Alfvén¹¹⁴. More recently, lab experiments by several groups¹¹⁵ and individual researchers¹¹⁶ have continued to provide solid evidence for the behaviors of plasmas while certain HEP labs¹¹⁷ have continued to provide excellent quantum data of for QED and relativistic analysis, which may prove in the end, to be the very next step towards the Unified Field Theory¹¹⁸. While there are several hurdles, isn't it true in life that that which is worthwhile to attain must be attained through hard effort, and not mere guesswork and trial by error¹¹⁹?

At any rate the author would ask that researchers, writers, scientists, etc... protect their ideas and reputations while still allowing room for cross-comparison and healthy, rational skepticism.

(6)

Once upon a time, perhaps, the publication in a reputable peer-reviewed journal may have been sufficient protection. But no more. In an age where people play loose with definitions and euphemisms may be used to speak on physics topics in different fields, which may be wholly inappropriate (such as "hot" "grains" or "flux ropes" or "dynamos", etc...), it is not enough to rely on journals. Furthermore, many journals are trash. They have ridiculously narrow or ridiculously broad requirements and viewership, or may be too restrictive as they participate in clearing houses with atrocious data linking requirements that are supposed to help but in fact place cumbersome barriers upon publishing authors.

Instead, the author thinks it best to use a widely known clearinghouse that is not too strict, such as ResearchGate.net or Academia.edu and use search engines to track social media and other places. It may also be advisable to get some cross references and citations, then place the research upon Wikipedia and other "encyclopedia"-esque References as a means of establishing primacy.

¹¹³ <https://archive.org/details/williamgilbertof00gilb>

¹¹⁴ *"Plasma cables seem to be reasonably stable formations which can be considered as structures important for the understanding of plasma phenomena. (Of course, their interior structure should be described by classical theory.) The plasma cables are either filaments or 'flattened filaments' (sheets with limited extent). They carry an electric current parallel to the magnetic field, and this is what gives them their properties. The cables are often very efficient in transferring electromagnetic power from one region to another. They are embedded in passive plasmas, which have essentially the same properties in all directions around the cables. They are 'insulated' from their surroundings by a thin cylindrical electrostatic sheath (or double layer) which reduces the interaction with its exterior. In the magnetosphere and upper ionosphere, the density in the cable is sometimes lower than the surrounding passive plasma (Block and Fälthammar, 1968). In other cases, the density in the cable may be much larger than the surroundings because ionized matter is pumped into the cable from the outside. By selectively doing so, the chemical composition in the cable may differ from that of its exterior (Marklund, 1978, 1979).... Besides the cylindrical electrostatic sheath, there are often longitudinal double layers, in which a considerable part of the power which the cable transmits may be converted into high energy particles. The double layers sometimes explode, and this produces excessively high energy particles."* ~Hannes Alfvén

https://www.plasma-universe.com/Birkeland_current

¹¹⁵ Thunderbolts Project, SuspiciousObservers, Ethereal Matters, etc...

¹¹⁶ Wal Thornhill, Billy Yelverton, Jason Gable, Dr. Peratt, Dr. Gurnett, etc...

¹¹⁷ LosAlamos, SAFIRE, Princeton, Lakeshore, Sandia, etc... <http://www.plasmas.org/fusion-icf.htm>

¹¹⁸

https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top-Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EP EMC

¹¹⁹ Much has been made about Edison's trials, but few realize how much research was borrowed, and how many inventions need be made first through honest engineering, for the first electric light bulb to be made at all possible!

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A final recourse is to join certain forums, of various reputability, and cross-publish (if not against policy) the work on all of these forums so that it continues to receive attention and is timestamped (for primacy). This will open oneself to additional (perhaps less savory) criticism and peer-review, but will give the public general awareness, as well. In lieu of forums, one may consider the creation and promotion of social media presences, such as a Facebook page or group, where the link may be put. This will increase search ranking and provide a timestamp as well. Twitter is popular for its quick citation schema.

Conclusion

The rise and fall of Dark Matter is related to a misdiagnosis in 1933 by Zwicky, as he was apparently unaware of the early origins of Plasma Cosmology. Big Bang began the same time, but with far less rigorous origins. COBE results misguided scientists into believing that plasma had nothing to do with the missing matter. But since 2016 a steadily growing distrust of the DM/DE hypothesis and of select portions of BBC have led scientists to search elsewhere for the *hidden force* behind certain behaviors, such as filamentary structures, odd stars which defy the fusion model, etc... and they have found it in quantum electrodynamics as a complement to magnetohydrodynamics. A likely merger will be forthcoming in the next decades as the mainstream recognizes, at last, the validity of PEMC and moves to co-opt the foundational work of PC/EU communities and researchers, albeit with *funny* and ironic naming conventions designed to sidestep the issue.

It is therefore advisable, according to the author, to make moves to protect the work of authorship, and promote educational outreach among the alternative community to cross-strengthen and enhance the community's "immune response" and receive the due credit, and avoid the same negative treatment received by scientists that have yet to receive posthumous accolades they clearly earned.

While it may be to the PC/EU community's long term benefit to allow the mainstream BBC to humble itself into quietly admitting it has a obvious need, and to come down from its place of excessive gravity-worship in order to understand and correct the data, in the interim the *merger* may form a sort of two-edged sword. On the one hand a shared common ancestry of a sort (1927 and previous, particularly 1900-1905), and thus a lexicon of attack and defense. On the other hand a new area of difficulty as miscommunications, misnomers, and misconstrued meaning will undoubtedly fan new battles for primacy and power to *control the narrative*.

The era of a Dark Universe is coming rapidly to a close. A bright - electrified - universe is dawning, with electric stars, planets, comets, moons, galaxies, and yes: quasars, pulsars, and black holes. The revisitation to BBC's assumptions, to general relativity, etc... will be full of promising achievement, once the era of wasted pseudo-scientific pursuit ends; late but not totally without value (they did prove the Electric Universe, in the end).

¹²⁰ <http://guides.wsj.com/small-business/starting-a-business/how-to-trademark-a-company-name/>

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